

Mementoys – A memory capturing and storytelling toy

Walid Hassanein – Tronics Design, Rd 87, bldg 5, Floor 2 Maadi, Cairo, Egypt, +20104717957, walid.hassanein@gmail.com

Rana el Kaliouby –Media Laboratory, Massachusetts Institute of Technology, 20 Ames Street, Cambridge USA, (617) 2538628, kaliouby@media.mit.edu

Abstract

This paper presents the notion of slow, long-term design to augment a toy's ability to capture and replay memories with its owner, and describes a framework for prototyping, implementing and testing this concept. Using a wide range of embedded sensors such as cameras and accelerometers, *Mementoys* capture information about when, where and how they are being used, as well as the state of the owner and then recount their stories many years later. We experiment with different materials, especially those with good patina such as leather and textiles, as they provide the best visual indication of age. Designing a toy for a much longer life span creates incredible opportunities for connecting pieces of one's life as well as connecting one's life within that of a generation.

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Preface

Sometime during my early 20's, my parents played back an audio cassette recording of a conversation I was having with my favourite toy at the age of 5. Although I had seen many photographs of myself as a child, there was something very powerful about remembering (or discovering) memories of my childhood based solely on audio recordings. This paper is an exploration of ways to augment the way in which we capture and recount childhood memories.

Walid Hassanein

Introduction

Why is it that people have such a strong emotional bond with their childhood toys, many years after they have ceased to have any utilitarian function? This paper explores the causes of these emotional bonds, and proposes ways of augmenting these through product design. Toys are one of the few artifacts a child feels they have ownership over [1]. When a toy has been with its owner for a long period of time, a unique emotional bond with the object is formed. Such toys ingrain memories of one's childhood; they bring nostalgia of youth, of playing, learning and discovering. A toy ages with its owner. Its mended rips and missing buttons are memories of time, scars, which are just as real as their owners'. Oddly, it is often these age-related alterations that trigger the most memories. Each wound the toy has reminds the owner of its causal incident, which in turn, brings forth memories of a certain era in the persons' life. Despite that, toy design is exclusively focused on the function of the toy when it is in use, but never its function as a life-long personal memento.

This paper presents the notion of designing to augment a toy's ability to unobtrusively capture and provide memories with its owner for an entire lifetime. Toys capture information while they are being used, and then recount their stories many years later. Each story would give the owner a flashback to a particular period of time in their life; connecting these flashbacks together provides an even greater story of their past. The toys use a wide range of embedded sensors that capture information digitally. Using GPS, a toy could capture geographic position and recount the tale of past journeys. Using tiny, wireless cameras and other sensors, the toy could also record audio and visual information, presenting the owner with context cues that would trigger different memories. We experiment with different materials, especially those with good patina such as leather and textiles, as they provide the best visual indication of age. Elements that have a strong possibility of tearing off after a certain period of time, such as buttons are encouraged. The toys would have a valuation model that would prioritize the importance of its captured memories. A long geographic move, or the moment when a new discovery happens during play, would be placed at the top of the memory hierarchy.

There exists an opportunity to design a soft toy that will tell the owner his/her story, by communicating a series of captured memories in a sequence. The toy will have a pool of memories from which to select and assemble different memories together to tell a tale. The search for memories can be based on several tags such as time, age, location, difference in location, and the owner's affective state. For example, the owner could request to view

memories of time when he or she were excited, from the ages of 1 to 8, strung together into a collage.

We draw on the emerging approach of slow, long-term design to develop *Mementoys*. Toys should not be designed to last one to five years, but for hundreds of years. Imagine a toy that shows you pieces of your grandmothers' and mothers' childhood, highlights memorable days of your upbringing, and in the future, will capture your own children's memories. Designing a toy for a much longer life span creates incredible opportunities for connecting pieces of one's life as well as connecting one's life within that of a generation. We begin by describing related concepts. We then describe our concept, Mementoys, and detail its various components. This paper ends with the results of our pilot study and our future plans.

Related Concepts

Autobiographical memories refer to specific events related to oneself such as one's 6th birthday or wedding day. Far from being perfect catalogs of our life, autobiographical memories are in fact creative constructions of our past, susceptible to many factors including our present mood and state, as well as our previous experiences. The ubiquity of cameras in mobile phones and other portable devices, as well as wearable cameras, has meant that digital pictures and video could augment and enhance autobiographical memories. An early example is MIT's StartleCam [4], which consists of a digital camera, a wearable skin conductance sensor and a laptop or other portable device. Images from the camera are captured and stored in a buffer in memory that holds say K images. When a startle response is detected by the system, the buffer of K images is downloaded and recorded, otherwise the buffer is replaced by new images. Another example is Microsoft's SenseCam [3], a wearable digital camera that is designed to take photographs passively, without the intervention of its wearer. In a pilot study with a patient who has limbic encephalitis—a memory disorder where the person has difficulties with prospective memory (remembering things to do) as well as autobiographical memory (remembering events that one has experienced)—SenseCam was used to record personally experienced events to form a pictorial diary to cue and consolidate autobiographical memories. Compared to a written diary, SenseCam's image diary largely improved the patient's memory for personal experiences. There is an additional effect of using SenseCam that is arguably as important as the clinical effects of the technology on the patient's memory. Merely knowing that she is able to go back and retrieve an experience, reduced the patient's anxiety, increased her self-confidence and led her to enjoy social events much more. Another example is DejaView's CAMWEAR [4], a wearable camera with a memory module capable of recording 30 seconds before the record button is pressed. While these technologies capture personal events, they are not designed as a toy for use with and by children.

As with the ubiquity of cameras, on-body and environmental sensors are increasingly becoming available to non-experts as wearable gadgets. One inspiring example is Silver's [5] Urban Exploration Toolkit, a sensor toolkit for exploring urban nature. In addition to a digital camera, the sensors include temperature, light and sound sensors. The project aims to increase children's awareness about nature, encouraging them to explore their surrounding environment and then creating stories about what they found.

From the moment children start acquiring language and a concept of "me" (about 2 years) they are taught how to use autobiographical memories to tell stories about their lives. Rosebud [6] explores the digital augmentation of objects to enhance their emotional value, particularly for children. Using stuffed animals, when the computer recognizes the toy within its vicinity, it prompts the child to type in a story about the stuffed animal, and in later encounters, calls the stuffed animal by name and recounts past stories that have been told. Rosebud relies heavily on typing and may not be suitable for young children.

Perhaps the most similar idea to *Mementoys* is that of Raw Nerve's Life is Suite [7], even though it is not designed for children. Life is Suite is a sofa that imprints upon it impressions that it may have absorbed over the years and stories that it had overheard. To unravel the secrets of its past, one must interact with the sofa, lifting its cushions and listening intently to soft sounds emitted from it. Like *Mementoys*, Life is Suite raises the experiential potential of objects that surround and accompany us.

Another highly relevant concept by German designer Akbiyik Volkan, is Camoria [8]. His concept ear mounted camera (Figure 1) initiates photograph captures when the users are in an excited emotional state. We assume that the camera measures the users' emotional state via skin conductance sensors mounted on the ear pieces.

Figure 1: Camoria (http://dvice.com/archives/2008/06/the_camoria_cam.php)

Description of Mementoys

The Concept

Mementoys is a hybrid toy that contains a memory capturing component and a storytelling component. The toy captures memorable cues, such as sound, video, images and GPS. The toy tags its captured memories with information about the child's emotional state, using facial and audio recognition, movement information, as well as skin conductance. The information stored in the toy can be transferred to a computer system, which allows users to observe the captured memories. Over generations, users will be able to observe and compare similarly tagged memories across family generations.

Almost everyone who's ever owned a stuffed toy is influenced by it – consciously or subconsciously – forever after. Toys have many different functions including transitional objects, companions. The toy will be a soft product, such as a stuffed animal. Although we will explore various forms, we have chosen to restrict the toy's form to objects that can be personified by children, such as a teddy bear or other animals. We will explore using a variety of materials in the toy, such as cottons and leathers, which communicate their age through patina. Also, the toy could have decorative buttons, which would likely rip over time and thus, communicating the story of its age.

Concept

This toy is a star-shaped soft-product (Figure 2). It is an artifact that is both familiar to children and has a form that is conducive to having multiple cameras. As this toy tags much of the

recorded content based on facial recognition, increasing the number of cameras increases the likelihood of capturing significant memories. The star form is also attractive because children are taught to ‘wish on a star’. We hope that this will encourage children to tell stories to the soft toy.

Figure 2: Star-shaped *Mementoys*

Use Scenario

1. Capturing Memories

A child’s relationship and interaction with this toy should be no different from that of other soft products that children play with. It is a toy that they will give names and characteristics to. They could tell their toy stories and secrets. They might even snuggle the toys at night for comfort. The unique aspect of this toy is that it unobtrusively captures these moments by automatically recording information when it is use, and holding on to the moments it deems memorable.

2. Storytelling

The toy transfers its captured memories to a database (home computer or remote site). Children’s parents, and later in life, the toy’s owners who have grown up, can watch memories on a screen using the Mementoys application. Users will define a series of parameters, such as

dates, emotions and location. The toy will assemble a collage of memories that fit the chosen criteria for playback.

When the owners become parents, they will pass on the toy to their offspring. As the toy goes through generations, so will its stock of special memories. This will allow people to intertwine memories that span generations.

Slow Design as a design philosophy

One of the major aims of this project is to design a toy that is intended to last for generations, with the intent of enriching the toy as it ages. Slow Design means using materials and resources in a way that respects the environment and tells a story behind an object. Carolyn Strauss, founder of Slowlab, stresses that products designed to last for longer offer a "deep experience of the world — meaningful and revealing relationships with the people, places and things we interact" [9]. In *Mementoys*, both its physical appearance and its bank of captured memories will become enriched as it ages. Thus, we will design for longevity through both the physical and technological facets of the product.

We follow the six main principles behind slow design —reveal, expand, reflect, engage, participate and evolve—as they fit perfectly with our goals for *Mementoys*. First, as with slow design, *Mementoys* aims to reveal experiences in everyday life that are often missed or forgotten by capturing a rich amalgam of experiences and events. In addition, the physical materials of the toy used will be chosen based on durability and patina. They should withstand the test of time, while also aging gracefully. The toy's patina in itself will tell a story of the product's life with its various users across generations. As the toy ages, its value will increase to its owners. The toy's appearance represents its age, as all the subtle physical 'imperfections' that the toy has acquired over time are revealed in its skin.

Slow design emphasizes the story behind an object or artifact, not just its perceived functionality thereby inducing reflection and contemplation. The technology within the toy will capture memories of many generations of users playing with it. As the toy ages, its memory bank will become enriched, the stories it tells will become more meaningful and revealing. Slow design encourages users to become participants in the design process – with *Mementoys*, what the toy ends up being and the story it says, will be a product of how child and family interact with the toy.

Finally, slow design demonstrates that richer experiences emerge from the maturation of artifacts over time beyond the needs of circumstances of the present day. A toy that is intended

to maintain its relevance over decades will create new paradigms in the users' perception of time, as it will be able to retell tales that have been captured across generations, exposing similarities in human characteristics that we often do not realize.

Mementos: Memory Capturer

Memory Triggers and Retrospective Capture

Several characteristics influence the persistence and recall of personal memories over long periods of time: (a) uniqueness; (b) consequentiality; (c) unexpectedness; (d) emotion-provoking. One of the questions that *Mementos* provokes is whether it captures those most "memorable" life experiences, augmenting these important personal events, or is it capturing experiences that would not have by necessity persisted in one's memory. In the former case, it would be interesting to explore what aspects of a memorable experience is typically recalled by a person, and how is that different from those captured by *Mementos*. In the latter case, we would explore the value of capturing typical events of a person's childhood.

Building on this literature, we design *Mementos* to capture life experiences—key moments of play, interaction and development—triggered by aspects of the external environment as well as the owner's affective and physical state. External triggers include a significant change in geographic location such as relocation to a new city or country. User-driven triggers include the presence of the owner or others, inferences about the owner's affective state and level of physical manipulation. Such a system could be retrained to capture states such as surprise or astonishment. Memory capture can also be user-initiated: a parent or guardian can control when the toy will capture memory cues. This can be accomplished using a wireless device, with a simple On/Off command. Once a trigger is invoked, recording starts, using a sliding buffer to enable retrospective recording. Figure 3 illustrates a time frame when the toy is recording, and highlights the events it deems as memorable, and thus saving them in its own memory.

Figure 3: Diagram of memory capturing sequence.

Affect Enable Capture

The user's affective state will be the primary determinate of what the toy believes is memorable and what is to be forgotten. Using a combination of facial, auditory and physiological sensing, the toy will capture moments that contain any of the following:

1. Laughter
2. Smile
3. Surprise
4. Cry
5. Story and secret telling
6. Exploration
7. Excitement

The toy has one or more tiny video cameras embedded within it. The cameras record video at a resolution of 320x240 and run at 30 frames per second. The toy also has an embedded microphone to record ambient sound. The cameras can be connected to a real-time face recognition module to identify when a person is approaching or interacting with the toy. The toy would also be connected to an affect analysis system that identifies and captures the owner's affective state such as smiles (captured using the cameras) or laughs and cries (captured using a microphone). The real-time facial analysis system developed by el Kaliouby [10] infers a person's affective state such as interest, happiness or confusion by analyzing the person's facial expressions in video. Figure 4 shows an example of the system analyzing a person's facial

expressions. The toy could also track changes in owner's skin conductance response and use it to trigger recording.

Figure 4: Example of view captured from one of the embedded cameras on the toy, and the results of affective analysis of the child's facial expression.

Playtime

We are also interested in having the toy record different aspects of playtime, documenting how play develops over time, in terms of physical activity (e.g., what aspects of the toy are played with) and social patterns (e.g, alone vs. with others). At the simplest level, the toy records the total amount of play with the toy, and the number of affordances that the owner discovers and the number of times each affordance is invoked. The toy has 3-axis accelerometers that capture the level and pattern of physical activity, for example picking up, throwing, dropping, spinning, and shaking.

Mementoys: Storyteller

The other side of *Mementoys* is playing back the captured events. The system will be able to string together a series of memories to create a user guided collage of memories, played back in a time sequential order. The toys' owner will be able to view past memories captured by the toy through a storytelling application. Users will be able to specify any number of the available fields, such as date and geographic position. Using these guidelines, the toy will playback a sequence of videos and audio recordings of the user to create a memory collage. When

compiling the collage we will explore different visualization effects that emphasize unique events versus recurring events and how to visualize the unexpectedness and duration of an event. Figure 5 illustrates a memory collage that is assembled by the toy, based on a user's selection.

Figure 5: Use sequence of collage playback

Storing Memories

When the toy is in the vicinity of a computer that has the *Mementoys* software installed, it will automatically upload its captured memories. We will explore the possibility of uploading the memories from a computer to a Mementoys website. Storing these memories in a remote, central location will allow users to access and share the memories from anywhere. Computer owners also generally update machines every few years. Storing captured memories remotely would eliminate the need for users to transfer their information from one machine to the other, and increases access to their captured memories for an entire lifetime.

User Interface Design for viewing collages

The proposed user interface for viewing memory collages will allow users to guide the content of their memory collages by selecting any number of the available tags. The Mementoys system will construct a collage by playing a sequence of its captured videos that fall within the selected parameters. If in a given field, for example geographic location, is left un-defined by the user, then the toys will make random memory selections. The possibility of randomness will create unique stories.

Playback of collages is controlled using basic playback controls. There is a play, pause, previous and forward buttons. The previous and forward buttons allow users to skip captured memories forward and backward during collage playback.

Multiple Users

The toy has the ability to recognize different users' memories. The interface allows users to select which users' memories they would like to see. If more than one user is selected, the toy will intertwine their respective collages into one. This again, will add an element of uniqueness to the collages. The user interface contains a window for selecting users. Figure 6 illustrates our concept UI, which allows users to define a number of variables from which the toy will assemble a memory collage.

Figure 6: Concept *Mementos* collage viewing interface.

Pilot Experiment

In our first pilot study, we designed toys that wirelessly log children's' play behavior through their interaction with the toy. The toys contain a set of sensed discoveries. Each discovery is

associated with a specific output, such as lights, sounds and movement. We tested the toys on 8 individuals, to observe and record their play behavior and captured all the information in a digital log file. Our pilot study gave us the opportunity to highlight design issues with sensor embedded toys, taught us about children's play behavior and helped us refine our logging mechanism design.

Figure 7: Pilot study prototype showing sensed discoveries.

Conclusion

This paper describes using a familiar object of play to unobtrusively capture special moments, for the user to playback many years later. We explore the notion of slow design and its advantages on a product of this nature, by designing a product that becomes richer as it ages. We see *Mementoys* as a tool for exploring memories and memorable events. El Kaliouby has developed and tested affect recognition in her previous work, and together we explored the concept of logging childrens play behavior in our pilot study. Our next step will be to implement the integration of affect recognition into the concept.

Does *Mementoys* memory triggers match those hard-wired in our brains? If they are similar, what aspects of the events are naturally captured as opposed to those captured by *Mementoys*? If different, what does it mean to have access to events of one's life that perhaps are not the most memorable but are as important in defining our experiences? We will study this question very carefully. A person could have a certain memory of a particular event, but upon seeing

that same event through Mementoys, their perception of that event will be altered. In that sense, Mementoys has the power to *alter* people's memories. Finally, we hope that *Mementoys* will provide connections within one's life and with family members across generations.

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